

Victims of communism and the struggle for the interpretation of history in the Czechia

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Let me begin this paper by taking a look at an event that, in spring 2023, may have appeared to be a minor internal dispute. At that time, a conflict broke out between the management of the Institute for the Study of Totalitarian Regimes (ÚSTR) and the employees of its Education Department. Complaints about bullying, censorship and inefficiency culminated in all 19 department employees leaving and a subsequent court case, which they ultimately won. However, as I will attempt to demonstrate, this incident is not just an isolated event, but a symptom of long-term processes and struggles concerning the interpretation of recent Czechoslovak history. It is the result of a clash between a polarised, strongly anti-communist interpretation of history and an attempt to view the past through the lens of everyday life and social practices. It should be noted, however, that this is only one level. Conflicts surrounding the ÚSTR have accompanied the institute since its inception, and it must be said that these conflicts are both historical-ideological and power-related in nature.

This event serves as a starting point for a broader topic that I am addressing in my research project, which is supported by the European Commission's Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) programme. My project examines political prisoner organisations in the Czech Republic and Germany, and their role in the politics of memory after 1989.

Although my project compares the situations in two countries, for the purposes of this paper I will focus exclusively on the Czech case and on the key question of what role the victims of the communist dictatorship played in shaping Czech memory culture. My analysis of the relationship between the Confederation of Political Prisoners (KPV) and the Institute for the Study of Totalitarian Regimes (ÚSTR) – the two main actors in this process – is based not only on archival research, analysis of magazines published by the Confederation, and analysis of contributions on their websites, but also on personal experience. As part of my earlier research on the prison system, I repeatedly met with representatives of the KPV. I would also like to note that I worked as an employee of the ÚSTR from 2017 to 2024.

1. From victim to moral compass: the early ambitions of the KPV

The Confederation of Political Prisoners was founded immediately after November 1989 with the aim of bringing together all those who had been politically persecuted by the communist dictatorship. In the first months of its existence, efforts to achieve legal and social rehabilitation dominated, but very soon the KPV began to develop broader ambitions. Its members saw themselves as witnesses of their time and bearers of moral authority, which gave them the legitimacy to express their views on the shape of the new democratic society.

The myth of the “anti-communist resistance” became central to the KPV’s identity and, at the same time, a tool for public action. This ethos was based on the conviction that resistance to the communist regime was as legitimate as the fight against Nazism.

This ethos gradually transformed into an effort to define the collective memory of communism through a sharp moral dichotomy: victim versus perpetrator, good versus evil. Political prisoners imprisoned in the 1950s saw themselves as “the first to resist the Communist Party’s takeover” and as continuers of the struggle for freedom. This perception of themselves as bearers of moral authority and guardians of the memory of the victims of communist terror became the basis of their identity and political activity. They felt that their suffering predestined them to become the “moral compass” of society.

They pursued their goals – thorough decommunization, vetting, punishment of perpetrators, and legal recognition of the Third Resistance – through public demonstrations, communication with politicians, and cooperation with like-minded organizations and, later, especially with right-wing conservative parties such as the ODS and KDU-ČSL. Their frustration with the policy of “drawing a line under the past” and their feeling of insufficient recognition of their historical role led them to radicalize their demands.

An important aspect of the KPV’s memory policy was to promote the fundamental importance of individual stories of suffering and heroism in the collective memory. This strategy was also visible in their work with the media and in education – survivors appeared in schools, in documents, and in the media, where their testimonies served not only as historical sources but also as moral appeals.

2. The ÚSTR as the institutional outcome of the memory strategy.

The establishment of the Institute for the Study of Totalitarian Regimes in 2007 was not primarily the result of academic debate, but rather a political project that arose from the long-term efforts of the Confederation of Political Prisoners and its political allies. The aim was to transform the moral ethos of the victims – based on a sharp distinction between good and evil, an emphasis on just punishment, and the perspective of the victims – into a permanent institutional framework. At the time of its creation, the institute thus became an expression of a memory strategy that sought to codify an unambiguous, anti-communist interpretation of history as the basis for a new democratic identity.

This political pressure, led mainly by right-wing parties and the KPV, naturally provoked criticism from the left wing and part of the professional community. Critics warned that the ÚSTR could function more as an instrument of “memory control” than as a space for open research. For the KPV, however, its approval meant the fulfillment of their efforts: an institution was created that was supposed to guarantee the dominance of their view of the past.

3. The KPV’s influence on the running and direction of the ÚSTR.

The KPV played a key role not only in the creation of the ÚSTR, but also in its early formation. For example, Naděžda Kavalírová, chairwoman of the KPV, was for several years

chairwoman of the ÚSTR Council, the highest body of the ÚSTR, which oversees its activities and decides on its focus. Other members of this organization maintained very close relations with the highest representatives of the ÚTR in the leadership. Through them, a retributive framework was imprinted on the institute's activities – an emphasis on security forces, political trials, the repressive apparatus, and moral unambiguity. The perspective of the victims became the starting point, not just one of many possible angles.

In its early days, the ÚSTR maintained close ties with institutions and organizations bringing together eyewitnesses, for example through conferences, the publication of testimonies, collaboration on teaching materials, and other projects aimed at popularizing the “correct” interpretation of the past. Specialized publication series focusing on the documentation of political trials and the activities of repressive forces were also created.

4. Conflict between two historiographical paradigms

Initially, under the leadership of Pavel Žáček and later Daniel Herman, the Institute for the Study of Totalitarian Regimes (ÚSTR) was dominated by an approach that promoted fierce anti-communism and a black-and-white, binary portrayal of the past, leaving no room for nuance and complexity. However, at other scientific institutions, such as Charles University and the Institute for Contemporary History of the Czech Academy of Sciences, a new research direction began to emerge that criticized this reductive view. Historians here emphasized the need to understand the past as a complex and multi-layered phenomenon, shaped by everyday life, institutions, discourses, and individual strategies.

This different approach caused tension between the ÚSTR and part of the academic community. In some cases, the ÚSTR took a very sharp stance against these new trends, including personal attacks and disparaging remarks. An example of this is the media campaign against historian Michal Pullmann from Charles University, which took on a hateful character. Muriel Blaive, who worked at the ÚSTR and was dismissed from the institute in 2022, was also sharply criticized. She is currently suing the ÚSTR and has been publicly accused of supporting the Russian regime, for example, which points to the continuing polarization in the perception of history and the role of historians in the public sphere.

In 2014, historian Zdeněk Hazdra became director of the Institute for the Study of Totalitarian Regimes (ÚSTR), striving to make the ÚSTR function as a true scientific institution. He sought to balance different interpretative approaches to history – both a critical, analytical view emphasizing the complexity of the past and a more traditional anti-communist framework. However, this effort to achieve balance and openness to pluralistic interpretations of history met with resistance from the Confederation of Political Prisoners and some of their political and media allies. They perceived Hazdra's approach as undermining the values on which the ÚSTR was originally founded and actively sought his dismissal and a change in the direction of the institution.

5. The Battle for Memory: Opposition of the Confederation of Political Prisoners to Changes in the Institute for the Study of Totalitarian Regimes (2013–2015)

Personnel changes at the Institute for the Study of Totalitarian Regimes (ÚSTR) represented, in the view of the Confederation of Political Prisoners (KPV), a fundamental and existential threat to the institution. The KPV's response to these events was immediate, systematic, and conducted on several fronts with the aim of reversing developments and protecting, in its view, the very mission of the institute.

The first and most visible level of resistance was public and political confrontation. The KPV immediately issued a series of sharp statements and resolutions expressing its full support for the dismissed director Herman. It further escalated its struggle by taking it to the highest political level, addressing open letters to top constitutional officials, including the President of the Senate. The aim was to mobilize political pressure and show that this was not an internal dispute, but a matter of societal importance.

In parallel with the political pressure, the KPV conducted an intensive media campaign aimed at shaping public opinion. Confederation representatives, especially Naděžda Kavalírová, actively communicated with journalists and systematically built a narrative according to which the changes in the ÚSTR were a politically motivated attempt by left-wing forces to take control of the institution. This effort was interpreted as an attempt to revise history, relativize communist crimes, and silence the voices of victims.

Overall, it can be said that the KPV's opposition to changes in the ÚSTR in 2013–2015 was a comprehensive strategy. It combined official resolutions, political lobbying, a media offensive, and strong moral appeals. The Confederation styled itself as the protector of the legacy of the fight against totalitarianism and portrayed the situation as a fundamental clash over the soul of a key memory institution, which it had helped to create and whose direction it considered its unquestionable legacy.

5. KPV after 2015: loss of influence and marginalization

After 2015, the Confederation of Political Prisoners entered a period of noticeable marginalization. The decline in the KPV's influence after 2015 was caused by a combination of several factors:

- **Internal paralysis:** The organization was weakened by long-term and exhausting disputes over leadership, which led to a gradual loss of members and authority.
- **Generational and social change:** The KPV failed to appeal to younger generations, and its original ethos ceased to resonate in a transformed society.
- **Transformation of the historiographical paradigm:** The memory framework of the 1990s, based on stories of heroism and suffering, was gradually supplemented and partially replaced by new approaches that examine the everyday life and complexity of life under dictatorship, gender, and environmental history.

Consequence: The KPV moved from its role as a key moral arbiter to the margins of public life. However, this vacuum did not remain empty. We are currently witnessing a new phase of politicization of history, led by the ÚSTR and new director Ladislav Kudrna who was appointed in 2022, which is closely linked to the current government (ODS, KDU-ČSL).

5. Conclusion: What does the KPV case tell us about memory culture in the Czech Republic?

The Confederation of Political Prisoners played a crucial role in the establishment and formation of the ÚSTR. Thanks to its pressure, an institution was created that brought the topic of communist crimes into the public sphere. At the same time, however, it contributed to the interpretation of history being confined for a long time to a framework that hardly allows for plurality and critical reflection.

In conclusion, I would like to make a few more general remarks. The case of the Confederation of Political Prisoners and its relationship with the ÚSTR reveals a deeper problem in Czech memory culture—the inability to accept a plurality of views on the past. Strong identification with one version of history, whether based on the experience of victims or on political ethos, can lead to history ceasing to be a place of discussion and becoming a tool of political struggle.

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